

Evaluating the Effectiveness of Instagram Marketing with Reference to Small-Scale Clothing Entrepreneurs in South Africa

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This study drew from qualitative research methodology to assess the use of Instagram as a tool for marketing among small-scale clothing entrepreneurs in South Africa. Data collection was through a multi-method approach, combining non-participant observation, in-depth interviews, and review of scholarly articles related to the topic. Different data sources were thus subjected to thematic analysis, where recurrent patterns and insights could be identified in the data. Theoretically, the study was guided by the Diffusion of Innovation theory by Rogers. The findings showed that Instagram is an effective means of marketing, whose platform has enabled entrepreneurs to overcome geographical barriers. It connects buyers and sellers from diverse regions: local, national, and international markets. In essence, the findings indicate that Instagram not only acts as a marketing tool but also as a catalyst in terms of innovation and expansion for small-scale clothing entrepreneurs. Its capacity for bridging distances and fostering meaningful interactions positions it as integral to the development of business in South Africa's vibrant fashion sector.

Keywords: Instagram, digital marketing, small-scale clothing entrepreneurs, South Africa

The emergence of social media has transformed the marketing environment, providing organizations with unprecedented opportunities to connect with their target audience (Kaplan & Haenlein, 2010). Instagram, with over a billion active users, has developed as an important marketing medium (Adekunle & Kajumba, 2021). The rise of social media has particularly transformed how businesses work, with the presence of Instagram's visual-centric platform, entrepreneurs and small-medium enterprises (SMEs) found a centre to display their products and services. Kwon and Lee (2021) maintains that Instagram's visual-centric platform is ideal for the fashion industry, allowing businesses to exhibit their items using high-quality photographs and videos.

Santiago and Castelo (2020) maintain that the audience initially uses Instagram to find businesses and items in the fashion and beauty industries and get ideas for purchases. However, now in this innovative digital storefront, a person can buy a product accessible for checkout directly from their feeds at the time of inspiration

(Sephora, 2020). According to Zeren and Kapukaya (2021), Instagram is one of the fastest-growing platforms that allows marketers to engage with their audience and significantly increase the likelihood that their customers will purchase online. Chu and Seock (2020) affirm that Instagram has been recognised as the most influential source of fashion insight. Silva, de Melo, Almeida, Salles, and Loureiro (2013) believe that Instagram marketing is an effective method of product promotion as a picture is believed to be worth a thousand words.

This article is designed to provide small clothing entrepreneurs with a comprehensive understanding of the most effective and ineffective methods of marketing their businesses on Instagram, a vital platform for fashion marketing (Kaplan et al., 2010). As Instagram continues to grow in importance as a key tool for reaching potential customers (Global Web Index, 2020) this research aims to equip entrepreneurs with the knowledge to leverage its features such as posts, Stories, Reels, and Instagram Shopping while also helping them avoid common pitfalls and mistakes that could hinder business success. By exploring both successful marketing strategies and practices that fail to resonate with audiences, this study seeks to guide entrepreneurs toward best practices in content creation, audience engagement, influencer partnerships (Al-Jabri & Sohail, 2012) and advertising.

Statement of the Problem

Pervin and Khan (2024) highlights that social media marketing has proven to be a fast-expanding strategy that helps companies quickly connect with their target markets over the years. However, the users of Instagram have different opinions about using this platform for marketing purposes. While some see it as an effective tool for marketing their services and products, some see it as a platform in which fraudulent activities occur, which makes it not to be the most effective tool for marketing. Blaga (2019) affirms that Instagram, like any other social media platform, has a risk of fake accounts. For that reason, consumers and businesses should be informed of the

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existence of online scammers. Astuti and Putri (2018) support the idea that a high possibility of fraud and swindling has emerged because there is no physical contact between a merchant and the consumer in e-commerce. The only means of communication between them is often based only on a set system. Hu, Manikonda, and Kambhampati (2014) also asserted that this new reality of marketing communication creates new business threats and opportunities. As a result, social media interactions increasingly influence buying decisions. People depend on their social connections before making a buying decision (Berger & Schwartz, 2011). Similarly (Case & King, 2017) add that one of the disadvantages of online buying is the risk of spyware infection on the user's computer system. Despite potential challenges to digital marketing, one cannot ignore the marketing opportunities it accords to entrepreneurs. The core issue addressed in this study is the persistent occurrence of online fraudulent activities that impact both sellers and buyers, particularly within the context of Instagram marketing in South Africa. The study intends to provide insights into how entrepreneurs can effectively leverage Instagram for business growth while mitigating the associated risks.

Review of Literature

The literature review captures the effectiveness of using Instagram as a marketing tool. This article solely focuses on the objectives of the study, which are to investigate the effectiveness of using Instagram as a marketing tool and to examine the advantages and limitations of Instagram marketing.

Effectiveness of Using Instagram as a Marketing Tool

The advent of the internet and digital devices such as smartphones have accelerated worldwide connectedness and access to information (Sarkari, 2024). In this innovative digital storefront, you can buy a product accessible for checkout directly from your feed or tales at the time of inspiration (Sephora (2020). Veleva and Tsvetanova (2020) note that digital marketing helps companies build trusting relationships with their customers and become more sensitive to their needs and opinions. Additionally, it helps organisations develop strong relationships with their consumers, be more sensitive to their requirements and understandings, and be more flexible and adaptive to changes in the external environment. Social media is no longer just a method of pleasure; it has become a major channel in marketing tactics (Redjeki, 2025). With over 2 billion active users worldwide, Instagram has emerged as an important social media marketing channel (Pandjaitan, 2024). Equally, Zeren and Kapukaya (2021) assert that Instagram is one of the fastest-growing platforms that allows marketers to engage with their audience and significantly increase the likelihood that their customers will purchase online. Chu et al. (2020) affirm that Instagram has been recognised as the most influential source of fashion insight. Therefore, based on the above arguments, the effectiveness of using digital media to market products, particularly Instagram, ought to be noted

Advantages and Limitations of Instagram Marketing

Advantages of Marketing on Instagram: Social media involvement, such as comments and likes, helps online content go viral and reach more people (Carr & Hayes, 2015). Instagram has a high presence in the online world, it has become the second-largest social media

platform and has a global reach that is continuously rising. Instagram posts lead to viral marketing and the visual content posted on Instagram or similar platforms like Pinterest is increasingly gaining popularity, claims Blaga (2019). He adds that a single picture can reach hundreds of thousands and millions of followers in hours. High visibility of posts - due to the large number of users, the posts can be noticeable among users. Ahmad, Salman, and Ashiq (2015) maintain that Instagram enables the fashion industry to connect with customers and understand their fashion behavior. The social networking site acts as a significant promotion platform in the form of fashion blogs, live streaming of fashion shows, and social fashion weeks, collecting diverse opinions from consumers. The influence of social media on the fashion industry makes the online presence of designers and brands inevitable. There are also high levels of engagement where the visual aspect and nature of Instagram usually lead to a more significant level of engagement from the users (Cuevas-Molano, Matosas-Lopez, & Bernal-Bravo, 2021).

Instagram, like other social media platforms, enables targeted interactions with customers and potential clients that are speedier, more visually appealing, and more gratifying (Blaga, 2019). According to Sashi (2012), by developing intimate relationships in long-term relational exchanges, customer involvement in the market transaction process enables customers to continue making purchases and even co-create value with the brand. Engaged customers are more likely to inform others about products and help the business by submitting user-generated content (Sari & Dwiya, 2019). Molinari, Abratt and Dion (2008) found a positive correlation between word of mouth and sales. Customers who are satisfied with a product are more likely to recommend it to friends and family, influencing their purchasing decisions. According to (McEwen, 2004), customer interactions are the techniques by which brands interact with consumers and assess their connections. According to Hollebeek (2011), consumer engagement is context-dependent, brand-related, and influences a customer's purchasing decision. According to Menezes (2013), marketing on social networking sites facilitates brands by enhancing brand awareness and boosting sales rates and referral traffic to their websites.

Disadvantages of Marketing on Instagram: The proliferation of internet transactions has provided fertile ground for fraudulent activity. Huey and Yazdanifard (2014) stress the fragility of customer information, stating that interactions between customers and marketers take place entirely through media platforms, enabling for the creation of phony identities. According to Conradt (2012), internet buying and selling has grown pervasive, attracting fraudsters looking to take advantage of genuine transactions. Zhu, Tao, Wu, Cao, Kalish, and Kayne (2017) underlines that fraud attacks pose a serious risk to internet enterprises and financial institutions. According to research, online digital advertising increases fraud risks due to its open platform and real-time transaction requirements (Wang, Gupta, & Rao, 2015). The underlying technology was not built with fraud protection in mind, resulting in vulnerabilities. Pureti (2020) discovered that phishing attacks and identity theft are prevalent strategies utilized by scammers. Furthermore, research indicates that social media platforms like Instagram are particularly susceptible to fraud. Gatautis (2017) notes that Fake accounts and scams can quickly spread, targeting unwary people. To reduce the danger of online fraud, Nguyen and Tran (2021) advocate strong security measures such as two-factor authentication and encrypted data.

Although Instagram is an effective marketing tool that many entrepreneurs use to promote their businesses, studies indicate that the platform still presents numerous drawbacks for entrepreneurs. These can limit its effectiveness as a marketing tool. This gap remains largely unaddressed as very few studies have been done to focus on the drawbacks associated with Instagram marketing. This study is significant in that it contributes to understanding the challenges that Instagram marketing poses for both buyers and sellers.

Theoretical Framework

The study was grounded on the Diffusion of Innovation Theory as expounded by Rogers (1962) which posits that:

The media make people aware of the existence of something new, and people will be interested in it and seek more information about it. After getting the relevant information, a small number of people will then try out the innovation and determine its effectiveness for its purpose. Ultimately, this is where the innovation will be tested by many people and subsequently adopted.

This proposition asserts that the diffusion of innovation is a way of delivering something specific to people's attention and how media consumers take that as an innovation (Fourie, 2001). The Diffusion of Innovation theory considers how the media spreads innovations through mass media and how people adopt those innovations (Turnbull & Meenaghan, 1980).

Rogers (2003) argues that innovations that offer a more competitive advantage, compatibility, simplicity, trialability, and observability will be adopted faster than other innovations. Adopting the idea is often difficult even though the speed advantage is obvious; thus, the availability of all the variables above of innovations speeds up the innovation-diffusion process. Based on Rogers argument we can conclude that, the more people see a product, the more interested they will become (Greenhalgh, Robert, Macfarlane, Bate, & Kyriakidou, 2004). Hence, numerous sellers use testimonials on online platforms such as Instagram to show that many people are using the product and they love it.

Rationale for Using Diffusion of Innovation Theory

The researcher employed the Diffusion of Innovation theory to investigate the adoption and utilization of Instagram as a marketing tool among small-scale clothing entrepreneurs because it provided a comprehensive framework for understanding the process by which innovations are adopted and diffused within a social system. In the context of this research, Instagram represents an innovation that small-scale clothing entrepreneurs can adopt to enhance their marketing efforts.

The diffusion of innovation theory as expounded by Rogers (1962) was particularly relevant to the study for these reasons:

Understanding Adoption Behaviour: The theory explained how small-scale clothing entrepreneurs perceive and use Instagram as a marketing tool, taking into account variables such as relative advantage, compatibility, trialability, and observability. Similarly, (McCloskey, 2006) argues that when a user view a new technology as more advantageous or useful than an older one, they are more likely to adopt it

Identifying Key Characteristics: According to Rogers (2003), an innovation's observability indicates how much it is visible to members of a social system, and its benefits are easily observed and

shared. As a result, the adoption process will be accelerated; potential adopters will no longer need to go through a trial period and can proceed directly to the adoption stage. The DOI theory emphasizes the role of innovation qualities including simplicity of use, cost-effectiveness, and social influence in driving adoption decisions hence its relevance to the study.

Examining Social Networks and Influence: The theory acknowledges the role of social networks, opinion leaders, and change agents in facilitating or impeding the transmission of innovations relevant to the social media environment, as Turnbull and Meenaghan, (1980) has already expounded that the diffusion of innovation theory considers how the media spreads innovations through mass media and how people adopt those innovations.

Investigating the Adoption Process: The adoption process is when a select group of people get the innovation and use it extensively. Following that, more people start using it (Fourie, 2001). The DOI theory is relevant to the study because it offers a tiered way to understanding the adoption process, beginning with information and progressing through persuasion, decision, implementation, and confirmation.

Objectives of the Study

- Investigate the effectiveness of Instagram as a marketing tool.
- Identify the advantages and limitations of using Instagram in marketing businesses.

Method

The study that this article reports upon was a qualitative research method, and its research design was the explorative research design. The exploratory research design was ideal for this study because it allowed the researcher to delve into the unknown territory of network marketing on Instagram from the perspective of small business owners.

Participants

The study population was made up of Instagram users. Both sellers and buyers active on Instagram whom are and have sold or bought clothes on Instagram. These participants were five Instagram-based customers and five South African-based apparel businesses with higher followership and frequent adverts on Instagram.

Measure

The study drew from the purposive sampling unit to sample its data. The purposive sample technique allowed for the selection of participants. These participants were chosen based on their knowledge as frequent online buyers and dealers with varied backgrounds.

Procedure

To collect its data from the sampled participants, this study used a multi-method approach. This approach included non-participant observation, Interviews and use of scholarly articles.

Statistical Analysis

All the collected data was analysed using the thematic content analysis to find and explain patterns in qualitative data (Terry, Hayfield, Clarke, & Braun, 2017). This technique enabled the researcher to investigate and comprehend theme patterns by organizing data into coherent units that were consistent with the

study's aims. The adoption of this method also facilitated the identification of critical insights and trends, driving corporate decisions and strategy creation.

Results and Discussion

The discussion below is based on the objectives that this article is guided by. The objectives are; evaluation of Instagram for marketing purposes, and advantages and limitations of using Instagram in marketing businesses. The study established themes under these objectives and they are summarised in the diagram below.

Figure 1

Graphic Presentation of the Findings as Tied to the Objectives of the Study (MADUKO, 2025)

Objective 1: Evaluation of the Effectiveness of Instagram for Marketing Purposes

Growth in Followership: The study found that when entrepreneurs introduced their enterprises on Instagram, their follower count increased. They earned a large number of followers; many people were interested in what they do, they clicked the follow button to continue receiving notifications whenever the entrepreneurs posted something on their pages. This resulted in more sales than when they did not use Instagram to sell. As a result, followers agree that Instagram is a valuable tool for business marketing.

In support of the above statement, the entrepreneurs highlighted that advertising their businesses on Instagram helped grow their businesses, as they gained a large number of followers.

Respondent B noted:

The growth has been exponential since joining the platform. The greatest growth online was from the lockdown period, as more people were home and online; the trajectory has been positive ever since then. Equally, respondent E submitted, "I was never an active person on Instagram; I would post and get maybe three or five reactions. After I started posting my designs, my page grew, and I started to have many reactions to my posts, above 100k sometimes." Based on the above arguments, it is proven, therefore, that Instagram is indeed an effective tool for marketing business.

High Customer Reach: The growth in the number of followers resulted in a wide reach of customers. Hence, the second theme that emerged during data collection was high customer reach. The entrepreneurs believe that through Instagram, they were able to reach many clients near and far in different geographical areas. According to them, the distance was not a barrier. Hence, one of the businesses, in the data retrieved through screenshots on media messages, replied to a client and said,

"Distance isn't a barrier my darling. Please check my bio for a link on how you can place an order online, there's also an option to add your measurements" when the customer said, "I wish I was in Cape Town. I am very far; this dress is gorgeous."

It is fitting, too, to hold that no matter the distance, Instagram assists both buyers and sellers in reaching their clients and working with them, irrespective of the distance between them. Similar to the above claims (Blaga, 2019) the literature review section also argues that Instagram has a high presence in the online world; it has become the second-largest social media platform and has a global reach that is continuously rising. Instagram posts lead to viral marketing. He claims that visual content posted on Instagram or similar platforms like Pinterest is increasingly gaining popularity.

Powerful Marketing Tool: According to the entrepreneurs, Instagram is an effective marketing tool because it allows you to promote your content and reach your target market in various geographical locations. They confirm that Instagram does the work for you, for free. All you have to do is work on your content to make it visually appealing, post it, and wait for the viewer to respond.

Respondent B further stated that:

"Social media in itself is a very powerful tool for advertising businesses. If your target market is present on Instagram and you can post and engage consistently, then it can work well for you."

Correspondingly, Respondent E submitted that:

"Many people love Instagram and are always on their phones. They don't have to buy magazines to see your work. In their hands, they have your work. Instagram, therefore, makes things easy for us as entrepreneurs. We don't have to pay to market our products. It is the best platform to market our businesses."

This means that one must conduct an extensive study on their target audience in order to gain a better understanding of them. They need to know if and when their target demographic is active on Instagram. This will assist them in determining the best time or window in the day to post their material for maximum attention and response, demonstrating that Instagram is a potent marketing tool. Entrepreneurs see Instagram as a good platform for marketing their businesses. Similarly (Zeren & Kapukaya, 2021) noted in the literature review that Instagram is one of the fastest-growing platforms that allows marketers to engage with their audience and greatly increase the likelihood that their customers will purchase online.

Digital Marketing: With Instagram being a powerful marketing tool, digital marketing was voted the best strategy over traditional marketing. The argument is that many people are always on their phones and on the go, making it easy for entrepreneurs to reach them. This also cuts the need to travel and get your clients, as you now work in the comfort of your own house and can reach all your clients instantly without delay. As much as digital marketing is voted as the best, some entrepreneurs prefer both; they believe traditional marketing is still relevant even in this era of digital marketing, as

some clients are still left behind in the digital migration. As much as digital marketing is a good strategy for marketing, we cannot ignore the fact that traditional marketing is still relevant; customers are everywhere: in the taxi ranks, shopping complexes, streets, corridors, and even in our apartments. That is where word of mouth happens, and you get to engage with potential clients physically; however, you cannot reach as many clients as you would with digital marketing. Hence, many entrepreneurs voted digital marketing as the best marketing strategy.

Respondent D: from the entrepreneurs reflected:

"I believe digital marketing is the most effective method to market any product. Even big companies are now resorting to digital marketing. Thus, a greater audience is found in the digitalised world. Everyone wants and can access anything on their smartphone. Hence, entrepreneurs should use this method of marketing. It is easy to access and customers who like your product can be seen unlike traditional marketing."

In the same way, Respondent E supported, the above view:

"I am old school; I still do much traditional marketing, but I would choose digital marketing because I get more clients through digital marketing."

Equally to the entrepreneurs' arguments. In the literature review, Veleva and Tsvetanova (2020) note that digital marketing enables businesses to forge strong connections with their clients and be more receptive to their wants and perceptions. It also helps businesses to be more flexible and adaptable to changes in the external environment, build effective relationships with their customers, and be more responsive to their needs and understandings.

Online Shopping: Just as entrepreneurs prefer digital marketing over traditional marketing, it was also established in the study that customers prefer online shopping over traditional shopping. Their argue was that online shopping saves time, as you do not have to travel to the tailor to order what you want, but you can communicate with them online and order what you want, and it be delivered to your location. No matter how far the tailor is, you can take your measurements or ask a tailor near you to take measurements of you, and then you send them. The above interpretations may justify what some of the customers stated.

Respondent A said,

"I prefer online shopping; it saves me much time, as I am a very busy with a tight schedule. I do not like going to the stores." Just as Respondent E argued and said, *"I have a very busy and demanding job. I have bought clothes online before and had my graduation dress tailored in Durban while I was in Limpopo. I did not have to go there; I just went to the nearest tailor and asked them to take me measurements, and then I sent them to the tailor; it was a smooth and quick experience. Online shopping is the best and my preference over traditional."*

Based on the above arguments, it is fitting to say that Instagram is an effective marketing tool as it also makes things easy for buyers who prefer online shopping over traditional shopping.

Influence: By nature, social media is a very influential site; people browse through their Instagram pages to see the latest trends hence, Buinac and Lundberg (2016) stated in the literature review that for one to have a successful business on Instagram, they have to learn what is trending on Instagram and follow these trends if they support their company. Concerning the media messages retrieved on Instagram through screenshots, one can see that others easily

influence customers to buy from the entrepreneurs; hence, the sixth theme of the study under the objective: "evaluation of the effectiveness of Instagram for marketing purposes" is "influence". When customers receive satisfactory customer service, they can easily say how they feel about the service the same way they would if they were unsatisfied. In addition, because of what they see and how it looks on Instagram, people are influenced to buy the product. Hence, in some of the comments on media messages one of the customers said, *"People cannot stop looking at me, the dress you made for me is too gorgeous man"* and the other said, *"People love your work, I have referred a few of them to you."* This is therefore proof that if people love your work, they will refer people to you and that is another reason why Instagram is an effective tool for marketing and how entrepreneurs easily reach people in different geographical areas.

"Do not be pressured by other entrepreneurs who are already at the top; they also started at the bottom. Stay on your lane, and post consistently, which will help you reach many clients globally."

The more you engage with your customers, the more they gain trust and start to support your business. Sashi (2012) also upholds that in the process of market transactions, customer engagement enables customers to keep purchasing and even co-create value with the brand through establishing intimate bonds in enduring relational exchanges between brand and customer.

Objective 2: Advantages and Limitations of Using Instagram in Marketing Businesses

1st Theme: Ease of Use: The first theme that emerged under the study's second objective, which is the "advantages and limitations of using Instagram in marketing businesses, is the "ease of use". The entrepreneurs confirm that Instagram is a simple application; it is very easy to navigate and understand. Considering the fact that Instagram is a picture application, you do not have to write long paragraphs of essays when posting; all you do is post pictures and wait for viewers' responses and interaction.

Respondent B stated,

"It is not a complicated platform, and besides, I was already a user of the platform and had engaged with multiple businesses through it, and as such, it made sense to create my business page."

Respondent E said, *"I am not a social media person, but I never struggled with Instagram. I post pictures and wait for clients to react and place orders. It is not a complicated app, and I love that about it."*

The literature review (Pham, 2021) also states that Instagram is easy to use and efficient, justifying the above arguments. Additionally, Respondent E, one of the entrepreneurs, said, *"I am not a social media person, but I never struggled with Instagram. I just post pictures and wait for clients to react and place orders. It is not a complicated app, and I love that about it."*

2nd Theme: Modification of Pictures: Instagram is an easy-to-use picture application. The second theme that was established in the study under the second objective of the study, which is "advantages and limitations of using Instagram in marketing businesses", is "modification of pictures." Entrepreneurs love Instagram because of its features that allow you to edit your pictures to attract customers; hence, the theme modification of pictures emerged. Herman (2014) asserts in the literature review that Instagram assists one in saving money on brand design since Instagram tools can be used to edit and

filter each photo taken for a product. This is a great advantage for small businesses still trying to find their way in the business industry, as they will not have to spend the little profit to hire brand designers to assist them in editing their pictures, but can now use that money to grow their businesses even more. In addition to the above argument.

One of the interviewees said,

"I do not have the best phone, and most of the time, I edit my pictures to make them look good; Instagram made it easy for me with the editing tool." Respondent C said, *"It is easy to use; as such, it gives you the ability to modify your pictures and make them attractive to gain customers' interest and have more likes and followers."* It is evident, therefore, that modification of pictures is an advantage to the sellers who use the application to advertise their clothes since it helps them modify the pictures to look attractive and attract customers.

3rd Theme: Tracking of Progress Instagram is not only easy to use but also allows users to modify their pictures. Based on the data collected from entrepreneurs, it was also established that the third theme under the objective, "advantages and limitations of using Instagram in marketing businesses," is "tracking of progress." Sellers love how Instagram offers them an option to track progress and be updated about their customers, engagements, and interactions. The above interpretations support what some of the interviewees said about tracking progress.

Respondent B said,

"You can track the progress of your business using the platform's tools. Once you figure out how it works, you can have such a vast reach". Similarly, respondent D said, *"Well, the platform has the right audience for businesses. As such, it gives a huge advantage to entrepreneurs, and you can easily see how many people like your products."*

Being able to track the engagements that your customers make with your business can be of great advantage, as it will help you grow from the criticism and compliments you will be getting from your clients. This also gives you a platform to engage with your customers so that they know a person is in the account, not a robot. Hence, in the literature review, Hollebeek (2011) argues that customer engagement depends on the context, relates to the brand, and motivates the customer to make purchase decisions.

4th Theme: Presence of Scammers and Hackers Instagram does not only have advantages; it also has limitations, like everything else. One of the limitations of Instagram is the presence of scammers and hackers. The presence of scammers and hackers was established as the common theme under the objective, "advantages and limitations of using Instagram in marketing businesses". This is one of the challenges that delays the progress of some entrepreneurs, as they get to deal with hackers. Also, some buyers become sceptical about purchasing online as they fear being scammed, and that makes a bad profile for Instagram sellers.

Respondent E gave a testimony of how they almost got scammed by a customer and said,

"I had someone who wanted to scam me; however, I quickly noticed and did not fall into the trap of his scam. The person lied and said they sent me an e-wallet and that I should send their shirt, which they ordered from me, only to find that the message had been edited. I noticed in the morning when I was about to go and withdraw. The year did not correspond, so they forgot to edit it. They should be extra careful of scammers".

In addition, Respondent B said,

"The platform is quite informal and as such there can be great volumes of messages you must sift through to get to your clients. Instagram is a public platform available to all, including opportunistic online scam artists, and it poses a challenge when distinguishing real customers from scammers."

They further stated that as much as online shopping is convenient, it is risky because people are likely to be scammed. Similarly, one of the sellers argued that Instagram is a public platform that is easily accessible to everyone, including scam artists, and that poses a challenge when discerning real customers from scammers. In support of the above arguments, in the literature review, Zhu, Tao, Wu, Cao, Kalish, and Kayne (2017) argue that fraud attacks are one of the major threats of any business or financial system, and online digital advertising is only worse.

5th Theme: Limited Reach: The fifth theme that emerged in the study is limited reach. As much as Instagram helps entrepreneurs gain followers and reach many clients globally, some say the reach is still limited, as they reach fewer people than they would have wished. Quoted from the data collected, Respondent D said, *"Instagram, like any other social media platform, is global, but it cannot reach all people that you might wish for it to reach, and that makes it the limitation of using Instagram"*, and Respondent E said, *"As I have already highlighted, I have only national clients not international. Instagram has not reached international clients; if they are reached, maybe they are not enough, and that is the limitation I am currently facing."* This disadvantages many small businesses, especially those starting on a flat budget, who expect their businesses to go through the roof immediately.

Discussion

In the study, it was found that Instagram is an effective tool for marketing businesses. This is because their followership increased when entrepreneurs began selling their items on Instagram. They claimed that after introducing their businesses on Instagram, many users started following them. They not only saw an increase in followers, but Instagram was also efficient in assisting the vendors in gaining an extensive client reach; geography was no obstacle. Drawing on the above ideas, the entrepreneurs concluded that Instagram is a valuable business-marketing tool. Because of Instagram's effectiveness in marketing enterprises, the entrepreneurs emphasised that digital marketing outperforms traditional marketing. Instagram has been recognised as the most influential source of fashion insight Chu and Seock (2020). Similarly Jin, Ryu, and Muqaddam (2021) also affirmed that Instagram is an excellent example of what social media can do for fashion branding strategy since consumers regularly see brand-related content integrated into influential people's stories and posts.

The sellers prefer Internet shopping to conventional buying, but traditional shopping remains a favourite for others. The study identified several advantages and drawbacks, the entrepreneurs hailed Instagram as an easy-to-use tool. They chose Instagram as their marketing strategy because of its ease of use. No degree or qualification is required to establish a business on Instagram; the platform is designed in a simple, understandable, and user-friendly manner. The platform allows users to change images and measure progress. Users do not have to spend a fortune paying brand designers to edit their photos before sharing them on Instagram;

Instagram does so free. In supports of the study's findings, Blaga (2019) also claimed that Instagram has a high presence in the online world, it has become the second-largest social media platform and has a global reach that is continuously rising. Instagram posts lead to viral marketing and the visual content posted on Instagram or similar platforms like Pinterest is increasingly gaining popularity, claims.

On the same platform, entrepreneurs can track their enterprises' growth based on the comments and reactions they receive from customers on their sites. Although some entrepreneurs agree that there are a few challenges on Instagram, the presence of scammers is one of the challenges that both entrepreneurs and buyers face when using the platform, as it is difficult to distinguish between a genuine seller and a buyer. Zhu, Tao, Wu, Cao, Kalish, and Kayne (2017) underlines that fraud attacks pose a serious risk to internet enterprises and financial institutions. Although the entrepreneurs acknowledged that this platform helps them access a wide range of clients, it was also observed that the platform has a limited reach since the entrepreneurs cannot reach as many clients as they would have wished.

Conclusion

As transpired in the study, while digital marketing, specifically Instagram marketing, is dangerous and can damage other businesses, it is also a terrific method to expand a brand. Instagram is, therefore, an essential tool for marketing. Not only do people capture and share their life moments with friends through a series of filtered pictures and videos on Instagram, but entrepreneurs use this platform to market their businesses and reach clients from different geographical areas. The pros and cons were successfully identified through interviews and media messages. Interviews pointed out some valuable advantages of using Instagram as a marketing tool. One of the advantages that the entrepreneurs highlighted is the modification of pictures. The users love how this platform gives them the ability to modify pictures. Users do not have to spend much money paying brands to edit their pictures before posting them on Instagram. Instagram does that for free, meaning they save money and use it to help them grow their businesses. The study used qualitative research methodology to collect, analyse and interpret data. The theoretical stance of the study was derived from Rogers' diffusion of innovation theory. The findings highlighted that Instagram is an effective marketing tool, as it allows buyers and sellers to connect from different geographical areas, locally, nationally and internationally.

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